

HEPATIC ARTERY THROMBOSIS (HAT) IS A DREADFUL COMPLICATION FOR TRANSPLANT SURGEONS, WHAT CAUSES IT?

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Abstract

Introduction: Hepatic artery thrombosis (HAT) is a critical complication in liver transplantation, particularly in living donor liver transplantation (LDLT). The risk of graft loss leads to the need for re-transplant and identifying another donor. Identifying risk factors associated with HAT can improve patient outcomes. This study aims to evaluate various risk factors in the incidence of HAT in Living donor liver transplant (LDLT).

Methods: A retrospective analysis using a prospectively kept database was conducted on 500 LDLT cases from March 2019 to Oct 2023. Data were obtained from electronic health records, including demographic details, full clinical data, liver-specific assessments (e.g. CTP grade, MELD Na), and surgical factors (e.g. ischemic times, surgery duration). Hepatic artery thrombosis (HAT) was defined as thrombosis occurring within the first 30 days post-transplant, confirmed by imaging. Statistical tests (chi-square, Mann-Whitney U) analyzed HAT incidence across all available variables. Logistic regression models were used to assess the association between HAT and different risk factors.

Results: By analyzing data of 500 patients (382 males and 118 females; mean age 43.8 years), HAT was recorded in 10 patients (2%) with annual incidences of 1.67%, 2.37%, and 1.99% for the years 2021, 2022, and 2023, respectively. The analysis identified significant associations between HAT and two factors: prolonged recipient surgery duration ($p = 0.001$) and increased cold ischemia time ($p = 0.057$). Other factors, including recipient gender ($p = 0.707$), age ($p = 0.611$), blood group compatibility ($p = 1.000$), and anastomotic techniques, donor arterial anatomy and type of reconstruction showed no statistically significant association with HAT. HAT cases exhibited a higher incidence of postoperative complications, including a 17.44-fold increase in mortality risk (95% CI: 4.52-67.28) and a need for re-exploration ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Prolonged recipient surgery duration and increased cold ischemia time are significant risk factors associated with hepatic artery thrombosis (HAT)

in living donor liver transplantation (LDLT). Although factors like recipient demographics, blood group compatibility, and anastomotic techniques showed no statistical association with HAT, patients who developed HAT faced significantly higher post-operative complications, including increased mortality risk and need for re-exploration. These results suggest that surgical length and ischemic control must be optimized to reduce HAT risk and enhance patient outcomes following LDLT.

Introduction:

Hepatic artery thrombosis (HAT) represents one of the most alarming vascular complications encountered in liver transplantation, profoundly influencing graft survival and patient outcomes. It is defined as the occlusion of the hepatic artery, HAT disrupts arterial blood supply to the liver graft. It leads to ischemic injury, biliary complications, and, in severe cases, graft failure which need re transplantation or patient mortality. In living donor Liver transplantation (LDLT) the risk of graft loss leads to the need for identifying another donor. The highest risk of HAT occurrence is in first seven days, inference of HAT are particularly striking within the first 30 days post-transplantation. Patient's mortality rates can exceed 50% in HAT, This emphasize the importance of timely diagnosis and intervention [1].

With the improvement in surgical techniques, perioperative care, and diagnostic modalities the overall incidence of HAT reduced in high-volume transplant centers but it remains an important concern in living donor liver transplantation (LDLT). LDLT presents special anatomical and technical challenges, including the smaller caliber and shorter length of the hepatic artery that increase the risk of thrombosis [2]. Reported incidence rates for HAT in LDLT range from 2% to 9%, depending on institutional expertise, patient demographics, and surgical protocols [3]. The etiology of HAT is multifactorial, involving modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. Prolonged surgical duration, ischemic times, anatomical variations, and postoperative complications are important contributors [4]. HAT risk is further influenced by recipient and donor variables, including as age, comorbidities, and vascular anatomy [5]. In order to reduce the

frequency of HAT, it is essential to identify and treat these causes.

A multidisciplinary approach is necessary for the management of HAT, with surgical revascularization serving as the mainstay of care, especially in cases where thrombosis is diagnosed within the first 48 hours following transplantation. Endovascular procedures like percutaneous transluminal angioplasty and thrombolysis have become effective substitutes for surgery when it is not recommended or is technically difficult. These therapeutic approaches emphasize the value of customized care, in which the intervention is selected based on procedural and patient-specific factors [6].

This study investigates the incidence, risk factors, and clinical outcomes of HAT in a single-center cohort of LDLT patients over a four-year period. By identifying key determinants of HAT, the findings aim to guide targeted strategies for prevention and management, ultimately enhancing graft survival and patient care. Through a focus on early detection, innovative surgical techniques, and evidence-based interventions, this research seeks to contribute to the evolving landscape of liver transplantation and the ongoing pursuit of improved outcomes for transplant recipients.

Materials and Methods:

Study Design. This was a **retrospective cohort study** based on analysis of a prospectively maintained institutional liver transplant database at Pakistan Kidney and Liver Institute and Research Center (PKLI-RCRC), a high-volume tertiary referral center for living donor liver transplantation (LDLT). All consecutive adult and pediatric LDLT recipients who underwent transplantation between March 2019 and October 2023 were eligible for inclusion.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board, and patient confidentiality was strictly maintained. Due to the retrospective nature of the study, the requirement for informed consent was waived.

Data Collection: Clinical, demographic, operative, and outcome data were retrieved from the institutional electronic medical records and prospectively maintained liver transplant database. Recipient variables included age, sex, underlying liver disease, Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) score, and Model for End-Stage Liver Disease Sodium (MELD-Na) score. Donor and graft-related information comprised donor-recipient blood group compatibility, graft type. Operative variables analyzed included cold and warm ischemia times, duration of donor and recipient surgeries, and details of hepatic artery reconstruction, including anastomotic technique and suture material. Postoperative outcomes assessed were the need for surgical re-exploration and 30-day post-transplant mortality.

Statistical Analysis: Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range (IQR), depending on data distribution. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages. Associations between HAT and potential predictors were evaluated using chi-square tests, Fisher's exact tests, and Mann-Whitney U tests. Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated for significant associations. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 20

Result:

Among the first five hundred liver transplants 382(76.4%) were male and 118(23.6%) were female. Mean age of male was 43.02 ± 16.54 years and mean age of female was 45.28 ± 17.52 years. Overall hepatic artery thrombosis (HAT) was observed in 10(2%) patients. In 2019 and 2020 no HAT were documented but in year 2021, 2(1.67%), in 2022, 5(2.37%) and in 2023 3(1.99%) HAT were documented.

Table 1: frequency distribution according to hepatic artery thrombosis and demography of liver transplant patients

Recipient Demographics	Category	Hepatic Artery Thrombosis		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Gender	Male	7(70.0%)	375(76.5%)	382(76.4%)	0.707
	Female	3(30.0%)	115(23.5%)	118(23.6%)	
Age Group	Peas		55(11.2%)	55(11.0%)	0.611
	Adults	10(100.0%)	435(88.80%)	445(89.00%)	
Diagnosis	Single	7(70.00%)	336(68.60%)	343(68.60%)	1.000
	Two	3(30.00%)	147(30.00%)	150(30.00%)	
	Multiple		7(1.40%)	7(1.40%)	

Hepatic Artery Thrombosis was independent from gender (p-value 0.707), age (p-value 0.611), Blood group (p-value 1.000). Among the patients 255(51.0%) were diagnosed with HCV, 69(13.8%) with HBV, 52(10.4%) with NBNC, 18(3.6%) with Cryptogenic and 17(3.4%) with Budd-Chiari Syndrome.

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of Liver transplants and occurrence of HAT

Figure 2: comparison of donors and recipient Blood group

Table 2: Comparison of Hepatic assessments and Hepatic Artery Thrombosis

Recipient hepatic information	Category	Hepatic Artery Thrombosis		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
CTP Grade	Child A		79(16.50%)	79(16.20%)	0.108
	Child B	4(40.00%)	232(48.40%)	236(48.30%)	
	Child C	6(60.00%)	168(35.10%)	174(35.60%)	
Type of lobe	Whole Liver from Deceased Donor		1(0.20%)	1(0.20%)	0.427
	Right	10(100%)	426(86.90%)	436(87.20%)	
	Left		41(8.40%)	41(8.20%)	
	Left Lateral		18(3.70%)	18(3.60%)	
	Auxiliary AR		4(0.80%)	4(0.80%)	

Table 3: comparison of surgical durations regarding Hepatic Artery Thrombosis

Variable	Hepatic Artery Thrombosis		p-value
	Yes Median (IQR)	NO Median (IQR)	
CTP Score	10(7.75-10)	9(7-10)	0.235
MELD Na	21(14.75-22.25)	18(13-22)	0.603
Cold ischemic time (Min)	45(33.50-82.50)	37(25-48)	0.057
Warm ischemic time (Min)	36.50(29.75-46.50)	42(33-50)	0.401
Duration of surgery donor	7.48(6.34-8.43)	7.20(6.30-8.10)	0.413
Duration of surgery recipient	10.98(10-12.26)	9.30(8.30-10.46)	0.001*

Mann Whitney U test

Mean CTP Score of non-hepatic artery thrombosis was 8.54 ± 2.05 (range 5 to 14) and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 9.30 ± 1.57 (Range 7.00 to 12.00), the difference was not statistically significant (p-value 0.235)

Mean MELD Na of non-hepatic artery thrombosis was 17.93 ± 6.61 (range 2.00 to 59) and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 18.30 ± 5.01 (Range 8.00 to 23.00), the difference was not statistically significant (p-value 0.603)

Mean Cold ischemic time of non-hepatic artery thrombosis was 41.10 ± 55.55 (range 0 to 1018) min and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 59.20 ± 36.25 (Range 28.00 to 128.00), the difference was not statistically significant (p-value 0.057)

Mean warm ischemic time of non-hepatic artery thrombosis was 42.59 ± 21.20 (range 0 to 398) min and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 39.00 ± 11.51 (Range 24.00 to 62.00), the difference was not statistically significant (p-value 0.401)

Duration of surgery of donor without hepatic artery thrombosis was 7.23 ± 1.41 (range 3.50 to 14.10) and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 7.47 ± 1.26 (Range 5.20 to 9.10), the difference was not statistically significant (p-value 0.413)

Duration of surgery of recipient without hepatic artery thrombosis was 9.49 ± 1.86 (range 4.50 to 18.50) and with hepatic artery thrombosis was 11.23 ± 1.16 (Range 10.00 to 13.00), the difference was statistically significant (p-value 0.001)

Table 4: comparison of outcomes regarding Hepatic Artery Thrombosis

Outcome	Category	Hepatic Artery Thrombosis		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Need for re-exploration	Yes	10(100%)	38(7.8%)	48(9.6%)	<0.001*
	No		453(92.20%)	453(90.4%)	
30 days mortality	Yes	4(40.0%)	18(7.74%)	22(4.4%)	<0.001*
	No	6(60.0%)	471(96.3%)	477(95.6%)	

Hepatic artery thrombosis was found associated with Need for re-exploration (p-value <0.001) and 30days Post-op mortality (p-value <0.001)

Odds Ratio for mortality among hepatic artery thrombosis patients was 17.44(95% C.I 4.52 to 67.28) times higher than no hepatic artery thrombosis patients.

Table 5: Technique of anastomosis regarding Hepatic Artery Thrombosis.

Variable	Category	Hepatic Artery Thrombosis		Total	p-value
		Yes	No		
Technique of anastomosis	Interrupted 7/0 proline		3 (0.6%)	3(0.6%)	0.811
	Interrupted 8/0 proline	1(10.0%)	67(13.5%)	68(13.5%)	
	Posterior wall continuous anterior wall Interrupted 8/0 proline		2(0.4%)	2(0.4%)	
	Continuous 6/0 proline		3(0.6%)	3(0.6%)	
	Continuous 7/0 proline	2(20.0%)	37(7.7%)	39(8.0%)	
	Continuous 8/0 proline	7(70.0%)	368(76.3%)	375(76.1%)	

Discussion:

HAT is a multifactorial complication that challenges even the most experienced transplant centers in the world. Our study identified significant associations between prolonged recipient surgery duration, increased cold ischemia time, and the occurrence of HAT, aligning with findings from prior research [1][2]. The prolonged duration of recipient surgeries was a notable risk factor. Extended operating times may exacerbate endothelial damage and increase the risk of vascular thrombosis. Park et al. (2019) similarly reported that prolonged surgeries, particularly those involving complex hepatic artery anastomoses, were associated with higher HAT rates [3]. Surgeons must balance meticulous technique with time efficiency to mitigate this risk. Cold ischemia time was marginally significant in our cohort, with longer durations correlating with

increased HAT incidence (p = 0.057). This finding is consistent with studies such as Stefanowicz et al. (2023), which emphasize the critical role of ischemic control in graft viability [5]. Techniques like optimizing graft perfusion and minimizing ischemic intervals could help reduce HAT risk. Patients who developed HAT faced markedly worse outcomes, including a 40% 30-day mortality rate and a 17.44-fold increase in mortality risk compared to non-HAT patients. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and intervention. Doppler ultrasonography remains the cornerstone of early HAT diagnosis, as highlighted by Segel et al. (1986) [6]. One of the main causes of HAT is the complexity of hepatic artery reconstruction. The anastomosis technique is important for maintaining the hepatic artery's patency, and a number of studies indicate that poor microsurgical technique or

problems with the anastomosis can result in thrombosis. For instance, the "W" technique, which is a popular method for hepatic artery reconstruction, offers better safety and reproducibility than other techniques (Kumaran et al., 2021) [4]. However, even skilled surgeons may have trouble getting the right anastomosis, which can cause complications like stenosis or thrombosis (Lee et al., 2011) [7].

Furthermore, variables such as stress at the anastomosis site, incorrect alignment of the vessels, or technical errors in suturing might contribute to arterial occlusion (Pinto et al., 2021) [1]. Studies have revealed that a large proportion of anastomotic failures are linked to these technical aspects, underlining the necessity of precision and skill in the technique (Piardi et al., 2016) [6]. In our centre, we have a standard protocol for hepatic artery reconstruction, which is why there is no significant association between the technique used for anastomosis and HAT.

Variant anatomy of the hepatic artery is another significant cause of HAT in LDLT. The right lobe of the liver, often used in living donor transplants, has a complex vascular supply, and variations in the hepatic artery anatomy, such as aberrant or accessory arteries, increase the difficulty of anastomosis (Choi et al., 2018) [9]. These variations can lead to challenges in securing the artery and ensuring adequate blood flow post-transplant, thus increasing the risk of thrombosis (Khalil et al., 2018) [10].

Furthermore, the donor's hepatic artery may occasionally be too small or unsuitable for direct anastomosis, necessitating the adoption of novel procedures such as arterial grafting, which may not always yield adequate outcomes (Kumaran et al., 2021; Obed et al., 2021) [4][11]. But in our study, we did not find any significant association between variant or complex hepatic artery anatomy and HAT.

Post-transplant immunological responses may possibly play a role in the development of HAT. The use of immunosuppressive medications or rejection events can weaken arterial integrity and raise the risk of thrombosis by preventing endothelial repair. Given that ABO-incompatible transplants have been linked to an increased risk

of arterial thrombosis, this is especially important in these situations (Kim et al., 2019) [17]. These immunological factors result in endothelial dysfunction, reducing the ability of the vessel to maintain proper blood flow and increasing the susceptibility to clot formation. Further complicating the vascular health of the transplanted liver, research has shown that early graft rejection or delayed graft function can raise the risk of HAT (Mourad et al., 2014; Piardi et al., 2016) [8][6].

The risk of HAT is significantly influenced by both donor and recipient characteristics. One important consideration in living donor liver transplantation is the donor liver's quality. Post-transplant thrombosis is more likely to occur in donors with vascular abnormalities, such as smaller or brittle hepatic arteries (Thorat et al., 2018) [2]. The risk of developing HAT can be increased by recipient-related variables, including prior abdominal surgeries, the existence of hepatic or biliary disorders, and poor general vascular health (Bekker et al., 2009) [12].

Additionally, the likelihood of HAT can be influenced by the donor's and recipient's age and comorbidities; patients who are older or have vascular illnesses are more likely to experience postoperative problems, including HAT (Stefanowicz et al., 2023) [5]. In our study, many risk factors related to recipient and donor were evaluated, and we found no significant association.

In order to effectively manage hepatic artery thrombosis, early identification and intervention are essential. The timing of detection is crucial, as thrombosis within the first 48 hours post-transplant significantly worsens the prognosis (Abdelaziz et al., 2021) [13]. When HAT is identified early, endovascular therapies such as intra-arterial urokinase infusion or thrombolytic therapy have demonstrated potential in re-establishing blood flow (Thorat et al., 2018) [2]. However, surgical therapies, such as thrombectomy or revascularisation procedures, are frequently required due to delayed detection; these procedures may not always be successful, particularly when there is substantial hepatic ischaemia (Park et al., 2019) [3]. In order to

identify early HAT, our centre used Doppler ultrasound every day for the first five days after surgery. Surgical reanastomosis is the conventional procedure used to restore hepatic artery flow.

Conclusion

Hepatic Artery Thrombosis (HAT) is a critical complication in living donor liver transplantation (LDLT) with serious implications, including increased postoperative morbidity, higher mortality risk, and frequent need for surgical re-exploration. This study, analyzing 500 LDLT cases, identified prolonged recipient surgery duration and increased cold ischemia time as significant risk factors for HAT, highlighting the necessity of minimizing these factors during transplantation procedures. Other variables, such as recipient demographics, donor-recipient blood group compatibility, anastomotic techniques, and graft types, showed no statistically significant association with HAT incidence. Patients who developed HAT faced a significantly elevated risk of mortality, with a 17.44-fold increase compared to those without HAT, and all required re-exploration. These findings emphasize the critical role of precise surgical planning and ischemic control in reducing the incidence of HAT and improving overall patient outcomes in LDLT.

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